

TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF NUMBERS IN ORAL TRANSLATION IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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ABSTRACT

Translation is considered to be a very important tool in all fields of Knowledge, communication and education. It is used to convey and share Information between different cultures with different backgrounds and it is 3 Considered as a means of communication between people around the world.

Translation is considered to be a very important tool in all fields of Knowledge, communication and education. It is used to convey and share Information between different cultures with different backgrounds and it is 3 Considered as a means of communication between people around the world. It Gives them the ability to communicate their thoughts, ideas, feelings, cultures and Notions. These equivalents depend on three main factors which are the nature of the two Texts, their objective, and the relationship between the two cultures involved. The Widespread notion of translation may lead to the appearance of errors. Errors are Usually seen in the written and spoken translation especially in lexicon, syntax and Semantics. Most of the errors found in translation are triggered by the interference Of the first language. The influence of the first language occurs naturally and the Translator wouldn't notice the error. Translation can be demanding since it may Affect communities or even countries. Therefore, translators must be competent in Both languages and cultures because wrong rendering may lead to a huge Misunderstanding, which evidently causes the translator big problems. These Problems occur constantly because of the novice translators' lack of knowledge in The target language rules and structures. It requires that writers and translators must have the Ability to express their ideas in the target language as accurate as they would in their mother language. Therefore, the problem of interference emerges when Writers and translators try to import linguistic structures of (L1) and force them Onto (L2). They also don't realize or comprehend that every language has its own Rules and structure and each one expresses ideas in different ways by different Means. The relationship between interference and translation is evident and clear in Different texts i.e. political. In order to understand the reasons that cause bad

Translation, we have to investigate interference from the first (L1) in the second Language (L2). There won't be any translations without interference as Malkiel Believes. He claims that interference would even occur in (L1) and confirms that it is not only a feature of L2 translation. Therefore, this problem should be Investigated from both sides in order to get accurate results of its reasons and Effects. What has been discussed above relates to translation theory, which identifies.

Translation problems and recommends the most appropriate procedure for Translation in order to solve the identified problems. So, translation can be Explained as a decision-making process and a problem-solving task. It is also a Complicated task during which the translator encounters some problems or Problematic issues which require observation, identification and finding the Suitable solution. The means by which the translator deals with these problems are Called strategies. Finding the adequate strategy for solving the above-mentioned Problems takes place in the decision-making process. According to Dr. Miremedi, translation problems are divided into two main Categories: lexical problems and syntactic problems.

1. Lexical problems. In the interpretation of lexical problems, Miremedi states That, although words are entities that refer to objects or concepts, a word in one Language may not be substituted with a word in another language when referring to The same concepts or objects.

2. Syntactic problems.

Note-taking is an essential skill for consecutive interpreters. Intended solely For the interpreter's immediate use as a memory-efficiency supplement, it is highly Specific and, as a result, largely incomprehensible. However, according to the Author, it still has some sort of system. Once the interpreter has mastered notetaking, he or she may be considered to have developed a note-taking system, which

Can be governed by certain principles. This work presents Rozan's seven Fundamental notetaking principles to help interpreters improve their skills. Additionally, the author emphasizes that excellent skills can only be acquired Through sufficient practice. Interpretation occurs when a person verbally translates what he or she hears Into another language. In general, there are two predominant modes of Interpretation: simultaneous and consecutive. In simultaneous interpreting, the Audience hears the interpretation simultaneously with the speech, whereas in Consecutive interpreting, the interpreter must interpret between chunks of the Original speech (or rather, immediately after the original speaker has completed a Few connected sentences or, in most cases, a lengthy paragraph). Since consecutive

Interpretation does not require well-equipped booths or a sophisticated electrical System, it is utilised in a wider variety of settings. First, the purpose of taking notes is to improve memory efficacy, not to Record every word spoken. Only with high memory efficiency can the interpreter Guarantee work accuracy. As excessive note-taking may decrease rather than Improve memory capacity in interpreting, it should not be overworked. Always Keep in mind that memory based on correct comprehension plays the most Important role in ensuring the accuracy of interpretation, not taking notes. As a Result, note-taking in consecutive interpreting should only concentrate on key Information such as time, numbers, proper names of people and locations, etc., that Are mentioned in a speech.²⁸ Second, the

interpreter's notes have a particularly unique personality. Practising interpreters develop their own note-taking strategies. Some use a large

Number of symbols, while others use very few. The notes of one individual would Likely be unintelligible to any other reader. Therefore, it is neither appropriate nor Feasible for a novice to replicate mechanically "a system of notes" utilised for years By, say, an experienced interpreter. A novice should not do so any more than a

Patient should utilise "a prescription prepared for someone else". With an understanding of the two unique characteristics of note-taking in Consecutive interpretation, it should be clear why novices are not advised to write Everything down or blindly follow veteran interpreters. Those who are trained to Become future interpreters should first strive to create a note-taking system that is Most suitable for themselves by drawing on the experiences or ideas of veteran Interpreters or interpretation researchers. In this regard, the section that follows Will present a number of useful principles proposed by researchers and veteran Interpreters.²⁹ In the Uzbek language, a plural form of nouns is created by the addition of Lar (s) to the core, and the emphasis is on the last syllable: bola-bolalar (childchildren, kitob-kitoblar (book-books), film-filmlar (film-films). In English, when creating a plural form of nouns, one common form for Numbers and compromises is made by the suffix € s, while other nouns have Special plural forms for them. For example: Girl's school; men's children's home. In English, the plural nouns are Formed at the end of the first word. In Uzbek, singular items are often made in plural form, even if it means one Thing or a person: Qalam, ruchka, portfellar oldim (I got pens, notebooks, Briefcases). Erkin, Shavkat and Hakimlar jonab ketishdi (Erkin, Shavkat and Hakimlar left). Determining the ways in which society is expressed is of both Theoretical and practical implications for the study of the structures of meaning that Reveal their differences and peculiarities. There are plural, general terms in terms of such words as bread, snow, cloud, Fog, and gasoline, which have nothing to do with totality but they have plural Meanings. When this approach is taken, all the related nouns in the language will Be related to the common words. Over time, the number of words that characterize Such a society are out of use because of social reasons such as aba (avlod-ajdod, Forefather, ancestor), abir (nice things), alqu (everybody, all, whole), budun (people, men), kull (eyerybody, whole, all), mardum (people, men). Later, Russian words came into the Uzbek language such as army, ensemble, Battalion, brigade, garrison, group, delegation, division, jury, board, troupe, Fauna, flora, crew.

In the modern Uzbek language there are such words that they refer not only To the whole or to the whole meaning, but to the general meaning with certain Meanings or meanings. Thus, in translating numerical words from Uzbek into English or from English into Uzbek, it is necessary to pay attention to certain rules.

²⁸Kriston A. The Importance of Memory Training in Interpretation. Oxford: Clarendon Press. 2012. – P. 79-86.

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